

1 Site-specific wave energy conversion performance of an oscillating water column device

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6 Abstract

7 The energy conversion performance of oscillating water column (OWC) wave energy converters at a
8 specific site is often studied by means of analytical models. Based on linear theory, these models lose
9 accuracy when viscous losses and turbulence become significant—more generally, when nonlinear
10 effects play a role, as they often do in real operating conditions. In this work we apply a novel
11 methodology based on a combination of numerical modelling and laboratory tests to investigate OWC
12 performance without these shortcomings. First, high-resolution wave resource characterisation
13 matrices are obtained by means of numerical modelling. Second, the resource matrices are combined
14 with the OWC efficiency matrices obtained through laboratory tests and, importantly, including the
15 effects of turbine-induced damping and air compressibility—usually disregarded in small-scale
16 laboratory tests, but relevant for full-size (prototype) devices. The combined matrices thus obtained
17 express, through a wave height-period distribution, the energy captured by the OWC for different
18 values of the damping coefficient. On this basis, developers can select the most appropriate value of
19 turbine-induced damping for a given site, based on performance values. The implementation of the
20 novel methodology is illustrated through a case study in Galicia (NW Spain), in which three
21 deployment sites are considered. We find that the turbine-induced damping must be matched to the
22 wave climate of the site for an OWC device to achieve high performance; indeed, changes in damping
23 cause variations in the total annual energy captured of up to 11%, which increase to 25% for specific
24 sea states.

25 Keywords

26 wave energy; characterisation matrices; OWC; air compressibility; physical modelling; capture width
27 ratio

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29 **1. Introduction**

30 Nowadays, renewable energies have become a pillar for energy sustainability, and constitute an
31 essential element in reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Gacitua *et al.*, 2018). In an effort to enhance
32 the role of renewables in the energy mix, the exploitation of novel renewable energy sources, such as
33 marine renewable energies, has focused the attention of the scientific community over the last
34 decades. In this context, wave energy is particularly promising thanks to its high resource availability
35 (Weiss *et al.*, 2018), low impact (Atan *et al.*, 2019; Özkan-Haller *et al.*, 2017), good predictability
36 (Carballo and Iglesias, 2012; Veigas *et al.*, 2015) and multiple synergies with other marine renewables
37 (Astariz, Perez-Collazo *et al.*, 2015; Astariz, Abanades *et al.*, 2015). The exploitation of the wave
38 resource, however, is challenging given the large variability in waves and, in particular, the large
39 extreme-average ratios. As a result, the development of efficient, flexible, and reliable wave energy
40 converter technologies is very much the focus of intense research at the moment.

41 Among the variety of wave energy converters under development (e.g., Di Fresco and Traverso,
42 2014; Oliveira *et al.*, 2016; Rodríguez *et al.*, 2018), oscillating water column (OWC) devices (Falcão
43 and Henriques, 2016) stand out for their simplicity. The only mechanical element (an air turbine) is
44 located at the top of an empty chamber, therefore not in direct contact with salt water. The chamber is
45 connected to the sea through an underwater opening, so it is partially filled with water. Wave action
46 causes the oscillation of the water column inside the chamber and, consequently, the alternating
47 compression and decompression of the air trapped above the free surface. The pressure difference
48 between the interior of the chamber and the atmosphere generates an air flow which drives the
49 turbine. A specific turbine design is required, capable of maintaining a unidirectional rotation under
50 the alternating flow. Axial-flow reaction (also known as Wells) turbines and self-rectifying impulse
51 turbines are the most common alternatives (Falcão *et al.*, 2018).

52 The performance of both elements, turbine and chamber, is closely related. In fact, among the
53 parameters that most influence the performance of an OWC wave energy converter, the damping
54 exerted by the turbine on the oscillations of the water column was found to be one of the most
55 important parameters, if not the most important (López, Castro *et al.*, 2015; López, Pereiras *et al.*,
56 2015). Therefore, it is essential that the influence of the turbine be taken into account from the earlier
57 stages of the design. The fact that the turbine-induced damping affects the performance of the system
58 implies that the efficiency of an OWC, even at a hydrodynamic level (before considering the
59 mechanical efficiency of the turbine), cannot be defined by a single power matrix: there should be a

60 different power matrix for each value of the turbine-induced damping (López *et al.*, 2016). Thus, the
61 structural simplicity of the converter contrasts with the complexity of its operating mode.

62 The hydrodynamic modelling of OWC wave energy converters has been mostly carried out by
63 means of analytical models based on linear potential flow theory (e.g., Malara, Giovanni and Arena,
64 2013; Rezanejad *et al.*, 2015; Zheng *et al.*, 2018), resorting to numerical methods for dealing with
65 complex geometries (Brito-Melo *et al.*, 2001; Malara, G. *et al.*, 2017). These models are inadequate
66 for non-small waves and non-linear effects such as viscous losses and turbulence, which are important
67 under real operating conditions. Therefore, the performance analysis of an OWC at a site requires
68 advanced techniques considering these effects, such as experimental modelling. Over the last few
69 years, experimental modelling has been used in the hydrodynamic modelling of OWC converters to
70 evaluate the performance of different geometric parameters of the chamber (Ning *et al.*, 2016; Vyzikas
71 *et al.*, 2017), to analyse the efficiency of an array of OWC devices integrated into an offshore
72 detached breakwater (Ashlin *et al.*, 2018), to analyse the enhancement that harbour walls induce on
73 the performance of the system (Raj *et al.*, 2019), or to measure the wave loads on the front and rear
74 walls of the OWC for structural design purposes (Pawitan *et al.*, 2019; Viviano *et al.*, 2016).

75 Experimental modelling is based on dimensional analysis techniques that relate the conditions in
76 a small-scale model (typically between 1:100 and 1:10 scale) to those on a full-size prototype. Thus,
77 to correctly emulate the real conditions in the model is of paramount importance to avoid substantial
78 errors in model predictions. An important aspect when experimentally modelling an OWC is the
79 spring-like effect of the air inside the chamber, which despite it being usually disregarded, is known to
80 be significant at full-size OWC converters (Falcão and Henriques, 2014; Falcão and Henriques,
81 2016); in fact, such effects were not taken into account in none of the aforementioned experimental
82 works. In effect, it has been found that if air compressibility is not considered, significant errors are
83 introduced in the assessment of the OWC efficiency, resulting in both under- and over-predictions
84 depending on the wave conditions and the turbine-induced damping (Falcão and Henriques, 2014).

85 In this work, the site-specific energy conversion performance of an OWC device was evaluated
86 following a methodology that involves an accurate assessment of the available wave energy resource
87 at the locations of interest and the thorough computation of the efficiency of the OWC device. The
88 latter was determined through an extensive experimental campaign in which non-linear effects—with
89 special emphasis on the spring-like effect of air compressibility—, together with three different values
90 of the turbine-induced damping—representative of three turbines of different characteristics—were

91 taken into account. Rather than testing the sea states of the locations of interest, a more general
92 approach was followed. A comprehensive set of sea states were tested comprising all the possible
93 combinations of wave period and wave height within the operational limits of the converter. The idea
94 behind this approach is to fully characterise the OWC for deployment at whatever location. The
95 performance of the OWC was measured based on: (i) the capture width ratio—the percentage of the
96 incident wave energy that is captured by the OWC in the form of pneumatic energy per width of
97 device—and (ii) the total energy captured in a year, which is ultimately the most important factor. The
98 methodology was illustrated through a case study in Galicia (Spain), considering three study sites.

99 The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the foundations of the developed methodology
100 are described. It is subdivided in three parts: (i) characterisation of the wave energy resource through
101 numerical modelling; (ii) characterisation of the OWC performance through physical model tests; and
102 (iii) calculation of the energy capture of the device. In Section 3 the results at the three study sites,
103 expressed in terms of the OWC efficiency matrices and the energy captured matrices, are described.
104 Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 4.

105 **2. Materials and methods**

106 2.1. Wave resource characterisation

107 The wave energy resource at each site of interest is characterised by means of the WEDGE (Wave
108 Energy Diagram Generator) procedure (Carballo, Sánchez, Ramos, Taveira-Pinto *et al.*, 2014;
109 Carballo, Sánchez, Ramos and Castro, 2014). This procedure is based on the *energy bin* concept
110 (Iglesias and Carballo, 2010), i.e., a trivariate interval of significant wave height (H_{m0}), energy period
111 (T_e) and mean wave direction (θ_m) of a certain size, allowing the reconstruction of high-resolution
112 characterisation matrices at each site of interest, so that most of the exploitable resource is accounted
113 for. The first step of the methodology consists in characterising the offshore energy resource along the
114 Galician coast. For this purpose, three buoys (Silleiro, Vilán Sisargas, and Bares buoys) (Figure 1)
115 representative of the deepwater wave climate in Galicia are used, covering approx. a 15-year period of
116 hourly seas states, which leads to an accurate description of its deepwater wave climate. At these
117 buoys, the most energetic bins, with a resolution of 0.5 m of H_{m0} and 0.5 s of T_e —the largest
118 resolution of WECs' efficiency currently available—and 22.5° of θ_m , are determined. With this in
119 view, each sea state is assigned to its corresponding bin and its wave power per unit width (J)
120 determined as:

121
$$J = \frac{\rho_w g}{16} H_{m0}^2 C_g , \quad (1)$$

122 where ρ_w is the water density; g is the gravitational acceleration; and C_g is the group velocity obtained
 123 as:

124
$$C_g = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2kh}{\sinh(2kh)} \right) \left(\frac{gT_e}{2\pi} \tanh(kh) \right) , \quad (2)$$

125 where k is the wave number and h the water depth. So, the total energy provided by each bin (E_w) is
 126 determined as:

127
$$E_w = J O_b , \quad (3)$$

128 where O_b is the occurrence of the sea states within each energy bin, expressed in hours.

129 Then, the most energetic bins contributing to 95% of the total available resource at each buoy are
 130 retained for further analysis, i.e., 720, 787, 693 bins in the case of Silleiro, Vilán-Sisargas and Bares
 131 buoys, respectively, which in turn represent virtually 100% of the exploitable resource. After that, the
 132 selected energy bins are propagated towards the sites of interest through high-resolution spectral
 133 numerical models. This is conducted by implementing three different models, each of them forced
 134 with its corresponding deepwater dataset, and validated against nearshore wave records ([Carballo,](#)
 135 [Sánchez, Ramos, Taveira-Pinto et al., 2014](#)). The model results are H_{m0} , T_e , and θ_m at each grid node
 136 along with other spectral information, and the resulting wave power computed as:

137
$$J = \rho_w g \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\infty} S(f, \theta) C_g(f) df d\theta , \quad (4)$$

138 where $S(f, \theta)$ is the spectral energy density. The information made available combined with the
 139 computed occurrence of the propagated conditions (the occurrence is conserved through the
 140 propagation process) can be used to reconstruct site-specific high-resolution characterisation matrices.

141 As a result, the efficiency matrices of OWC converters can be combined with the resulting resource
 142 information to determine any performance parameter of specific OWC-site combinations.

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Figure 1. Locations of the three study sites in Galicia (NW Spain).

146 *2.1.1. Selection of study sites*

147 In order to illustrate the methodology proposed, three sites in the Galician nearshore of interest for
 148 installing an OWC converter were selected (NW Spain). The location of the three selected sites,
 149 Cariño (1), Corme (2) and Panxón (3), is presented in Figure 1 and their UTM coordinates and depth
 150 are included in Table 1.

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Table 1. Easting (X) and northing (Y) coordinates (UTM29N/ETRS89) and water depth (h) of the three study sites.

Study site	X	Y	h
Cariño (1)	591770 m	4843092 m	12.7 m
Corme (2)	502782 m	4789545 m	12.0 m
Panxón (3)	513645 m	4665291 m	10.1 m

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The three sites correspond to small to medium ports that are suitable for the installation of a breakwater-integrated OWC thanks to their characteristics—mainly, bathymetry and wave exposure. Furthermore, in an attempt to represent different wave energy distributions, the study sites cover different geographic areas: site 1, the North coast of Galicia; site 2, the so-called Death Coast (*Costa da Morte*), extending from Cape Finisterre to Cape San Adrián (Figure 1); and site 3, the Southwest coast or *Rías Baixas*.

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Figure 2. Wave resource characterisation matrices in an average year for the three selected study sites. The colour scale represents the total energy per metre of wave front (E_w) provided by each energy bin; the numbers indicate the occurrence of the sea states within each energy bin, expressed in hours; and the isolines provide the wave power.

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The wave resource characterisation matrices of these three study sites are presented in Figure 2.

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The matrices were discretised in bins of $0.5 \text{ s } (\Delta T_e) \times 0.5 \text{ m } (\Delta H_{m0})$. The three locations present a

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moderate wave climate, with values of the total energy per metre of wave front in an average year of

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27.14 , 27.06 and 21.49 MWhm^{-1} , for Cariño (1), Corme (2) and Panxón (3), respectively. Despite

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these rather similar average values, the wave resource distribution across energy periods is markedly

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different at the three sites. At site 1 most of the energy is provided by sea states with energy periods

170 between 6 and 8 s; at site 2, the energy is concentrated in energy periods between 8 and 10 s; finally,
171 at site 3, the bulk of the energy is supplied by sea states with energy periods between 9.5 and 11 s.
172 This is likely due to the fetch increasing from site 1, which is exposed to the Bay of Biscay, to site 3,
173 exposed to the North Atlantic Ocean. Regarding the resource distribution across significant wave
174 heights, the most energetic sea states correspond with wave heights between 1.0 and 2.5 m at the three
175 study sites, with a slight deviation towards the lower values in the case of site 3.

176 2.2. OWC performance characterisation

177 2.2.1. Physical modelling

178 The physical model represents, at a 1:25 scale ratio, a standard design of breakwater-integrated OWC
179 wave energy converter (Figure 3a). Taking into account that the construction costs are one of the main
180 downsides of OWC technology, multi-purpose solutions constitute an interesting and more feasible
181 approach. With this as background, a breakwater-integrated OWC enables both coastal protection and
182 energy harnessing by means of a sole structure, thereby maximising the benefits and minimising the
183 costs. The OWC model tested in this work (Figure 3b) is two-dimensional, its width matching that of
184 the wave flume. The model and prototype dimensions are presented in Table 2.

185 As previously mentioned, the damping exerted by the turbine on the water column oscillation is
186 one of the most important factors, if not the most important one, affecting the efficiency of an OWC
187 converter. Therefore, modelling the turbine-induced damping is a prerequisite for obtaining reliable
188 results. In this work, the turbine-induced damping was modelled through an orifice (e.g., Perez-
189 Collazo *et al.*, 2018; Vyzikas *et al.*, 2017), i.e., an element introducing a pressure drop which varies
190 quadratically with the flow rate, and therefore appropriately reproducing the behaviour of a self-
191 rectifying impulse turbine (Falcão and Henriques, 2016). In comparison to Wells turbines, impulse
192 turbines present a series of characteristics that make them particularly interesting for breakwater-
193 integrated OWC converters: smaller diameter, lower rotational speed and consequently lower levels of
194 noise. In addition, impulse turbines present a smoother efficiency curve, i.e., a good performance over
195 a broader range of flow conditions. Three different orifices of diameter $D = 28, 31$ and 39 mm were
196 tested, corresponding to opening ratios (ratio of the orifice area to the plan area of the OWC chamber)
197 of 0.8%, 1.0% and 1.5%, respectively. The three orifices are representative of three impulse turbines
198 of different diameter—for self-rectifying impulse turbines, the relationship between pressure drop and
199 flow rate is not significantly affected by changes in rotational speed (Falcão and Henriques, 2014).

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Figure 3. Sketch of a breakwater-integrated OWC (A) and views of the tested OWC converter (B).

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Table 2. Dimensions of the geometrical parameters of the OWC converter.

Geometrical parameter	Symbol	Model dimensions	Prototype dimensions
Chamber height	h_c	63.6 cm	15.9 m
Chamber length (in the wave direction)	l_c	12.8 cm	3.2 m
Entrance height	h_e	12.8 cm	3.2 m
Vertical walls thickness	t_z	2.0 cm	0.5 m
Horizontal walls thickness	t_x	2.8 cm	0.7 m
Orifice diameter	D	Variable	—
Duct height	h_d	$25D$	—
Bedding height	h_b	8.0 cm	2.0 m
Bedding length	l_b	20.0 cm	5.0 m
Bedding slope	s	1:2	1:2

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The scaling of the model was based on Froude's similitude, i.e., equal ratio of inertia to gravity

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forces between model and prototype. This is a mandatory assumption when dealing with free surface

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flows (Hughes, 1993). However, in the case of OWC wave energy converters, the spring-like effect of

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the air inside the chamber is known to play an important role, which calls for maintaining also an

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equal ratio of inertia to air compression forces between model and prototype (Weber, 2007). To this

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end the air chamber volume must be scaled according to (Falcão and Henriques, 2014):

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$$\frac{V_m}{V_p} = \frac{n_m}{n_p} \lambda^{-2} \delta^{-1}, \quad (5)$$

210 where the subscripts m and p refer to model and prototype, respectively; V is the volume of the air
 211 chamber; n is the polytropic exponent of the turbine, which takes the values $n_p = 1.2$ and $n_m = 1.0$ for a
 212 full-size turbine and for an orifice, respectively; λ is the scale factor ($\lambda = 25$); and δ is the water
 213 density ratio (ρ_m/ρ_p), which takes a value of $\delta = 0.98$ for wave flume testing.

214 The approach to meeting both aforementioned requirements is to apply the Froude similitude
 215 criterion and perfect geometric similarity in the hydrodynamic domain (wet part of the model) but
 216 considering a distorted aerodynamic domain (upper part of the chamber) that fulfils Eq. (5). The
 217 required volume was achieved by connecting the air chamber to a rigid-walled air reservoir of an
 218 adequate volume (Figure 5). This is the procedure recommended for OWC small-scale modelling as
 219 stated by Falcão and Henriques (2014). By applying Eq. (5), the volume of the air chamber at model
 220 scale should be $V_m = 538.4 \text{ dm}^3$, which makes it necessary to add to the chamber a volume of
 221 513.2 dm^3 .

222
 223 Figure 4. Experimental set-up of the model OWC.

224 Physical model tests were carried out in the wave flume of the University of Santiago de
 225 Compostela (USC), with dimensions of $20 \text{ m} \times 0.65 \text{ m}$ in plan view. It is equipped with a piston
 226 paddle wave generation system with active absorption of the reflected waves. The experimental set-up
 227 is presented in Figure 4. A total of nine wave gauges were installed to monitor the wave propagation,
 228 analyse the incident and reflected wave field, and check the absence of transverse waves.
 229 Additionally, two ultrasonic level sensors were placed inside the chamber to measure the oscillations
 230 of the water column. Finally, a differential pressure sensor registered the time-varying pressure drop
 231 between the atmosphere and the interior of the chamber.

232 The experimental campaign comprised 49 irregular wave conditions (Figure 5), representative of
 233 as many omnidirectional *energy bins* (Carballo, Sánchez, Ramos and Castro, 2014), or bivariate
 234 intervals that discretise the sea states according to their H_{m0} and T_e . Thus, all the sea states with a
 235 significant wave height and an energy period within the range of an energy bin are assumed to be
 236 represented by a single capture width ratio—corresponding to the wave conditions representative of
 237 the energy bin. The smaller the size of the energy bins, the greater the precision of the performance
 238 matrix. In this work, an interval size of 1.0 m for significant wave height and 1.0 s for energy period
 239 were used.

240
 241 Figure 5. Sea states covered in the experimental campaign. The grey axes represent the boundaries of
 242 the sea states and the black axes the representative wave conditions tested. The crosses indicate the
 243 representative wave condition of each energy bin.

244 The selection of the representative wave conditions of each energy bin is, therefore, of
 245 paramount importance. As wave energy varies linearly with energy period, the representative energy
 246 period was set to the arithmetic mean of the energy periods at the limits of the bin. However, wave
 247 energy varies quadratically with the significant wave height, so the representative value should
 248 provide the mean wave energy of the bin, satisfying the following equation:

$$249 \int_{H_1}^{H_R} H^2 dH = \int_{H_R}^{H_2} H^2 dH \quad (6)$$

250 where H_1 and H_2 are the wave height at the limits of each bin; and H_R is the representative value of the
 251 wave height of that bin (Carballo, Sánchez, Ramos, Taveira-Pinto *et al.*, 2014).

252 The 49 selected bins cover energy periods from 4 to 15 s and wave heights from 0 to 5 m (limit
 253 established based on the characteristics of the OWC). For the selected study sites the 49 bins cover
 254 more than 99% of the energy and time of the wave resource matrices presented in Figure 2 for the
 255 three study sites.

256 In order to experimentally test the representative wave conditions, it is necessary to assign to
 257 each of them a wave energy frequency distribution, i.e., a frequency spectral density function or wave
 258 spectrum. The wave spectrum better representing the wave conditions at the region of interest is the
 259 JONSWAP spectrum (Carballo *et al.*, 2015), that is given by the form (Hasselmann *et al.*, 1973):

$$260 \quad S_J(f) = \alpha g^2 (2\pi)^{-4} f^{-5} \exp\left(-\frac{5}{4}\left(\frac{f}{f_p}\right)^{-4}\right) \gamma^{\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{f/f_p-1}{\sigma}\right)^2\right)}, \quad (7)$$

261 where α is a scaling parameter, f_p is the peak frequency (the reciprocal of the peak period), γ is the
 262 peak enhancement factor and σ is a spectral shape parameter that takes the following values:

$$263 \quad \sigma = \begin{cases} 0.07 & \text{for } f < f_p \\ 0.09 & \text{for } f \geq f_p \end{cases}. \quad (8)$$

264 The scaling parameter α was adjusted in order to obtain, through numerical integration of the
 265 spectrum, the desired value of the significant wave height for each wave condition. For the peak
 266 enhancement factor, based on previous works at the same location (Areal *et al.*, 2017), a value of
 267 $\gamma = 3.3$ was selected. The peak period of each wave condition was calculated from the energy periods
 268 defined in Figure 5, using the ratio:

$$269 \quad \frac{T_e}{T_p} = 0.90, \quad (9)$$

270 which corresponds to JONSWAP-type spectra with a peak enhancement factor of 3.3 (Goda, 2010).

271 Each of the 49 irregular wave conditions was tested for the three orifice diameters—in total, 147
 272 irregular wave tests were conducted. Testing times vary depending on the period of each wave
 273 condition in order to ensure that, at least, 200 waves were generated, a number large enough to
 274 decrease the sampling variation of the wave statistics (Goda, 2010).

275 2.2.2. Calculation of the efficiency matrices

276 The performance of the OWC under the wave conditions representative of each energy bin was
 277 characterised based on the capture width ratio (also known as relative capture width), which reflects
 278 the fraction of the wave power flowing through the device that is absorbed by the device (Babarit,
 279 2015), defined by

$$280 \quad C_{WR} = \frac{P_p}{P_w w}, \quad (10)$$

281 where P_p is the mean pneumatic power absorbed by the OWC; P_w is the mean available wave power
 282 per unit width of wave front; and w is the width of the OWC chamber (transverse to wave direction).
 283 The mean pneumatic power is defined as

$$284 \quad P_p = \frac{1}{t_{max}} \int_0^{t_{max}} \Delta p Q dt , \quad (11)$$

285 where t_{max} is the time duration of each test; Δp is the pressure drop directly measured by the
 286 differential pressure sensor; and Q is the air flow rate through the orifice calculated as

$$287 \quad Q = \text{sgn}(\Delta p) \left(\frac{B_r}{|\Delta p|} \right)^{1/2} , \quad (12)$$

288 being B_r a damping parameter which represents the pressure-flowrate relationship for each orifice,
 289 obtained in the present case through numerical and physical modelling following the definition as
 290 provided by López *et al.* (2015):

$$291 \quad B^* = \frac{\Delta p^{1/2}}{Q} \frac{A_c}{\rho_a^{1/2}} = B_r^{1/2} \frac{A_c}{\rho_a^{1/2}} , \quad (13)$$

292 where A_c is the water plane area of the OWC chamber ($A_c = l_c \times w$); and ρ_a is the air density. For the
 293 three orifice diameters, $D = 28, 31$ and 39 mm, these parameters take the values $B_r = 5.30 \times 10^6$,
 294 3.59×10^6 and 1.48×10^6 kg/m⁷ (in model dimensions) and $B^* = 160.49, 132.18$ and 84.85 ,
 295 respectively.

296 The mean wave power per unit width of wave front is given by

$$297 \quad P_w = \rho_w g \int_0^\infty S(f) C_g(f) df , \quad (14)$$

298 where $S(f)$ is the incident spectral energy density; and $C_g(f)$ is the group velocity of each frequency
 299 band.

300 2.3. Energy capture

301 Finally, the pneumatic energy captured by the OWC for the three values of the turbine-induced
 302 damping at the three study sites was calculated. First, the pneumatic power captured by each i -th
 303 energy bin ($E_{p,i}$) was obtained following:

$$304 \quad E_{p,i} = C_{WR,i} E_{w,i} . \quad (15)$$

305 where $C_{WR,i}$ and $E_{w,i}$ are the capture width ratio and the available wave energy of each i -th energy bin,
 306 respectively. As there are three efficiency matrices—one for each value of turbine-induced damping—

307 and three wave resource characterisation matrices—one for each study site—there will be nine
 308 different energy capture matrices.

309 Second, the total annual available energy and the total annual captured energy was calculated,
 310 respectively, as:

$$311 \quad E_{w, annual} = \sum_{i=1}^N E_{w, i} \quad , \quad (16)$$

$$312 \quad E_{p, annual} = \sum_{i=1}^N E_{p, i} \quad , \quad (17)$$

313 where N is the number of energy bins of each matrix. Last, the annual capture width ratio was
 314 calculated as:

$$315 \quad C_{WR, annual} = \frac{E_{p, annual}}{E_{w, annual}} \quad . \quad (18)$$

316 3. Results

317 3.1. OWC efficiency matrices

318 The efficiency matrices of the OWC wave energy converter, obtained through the experimental
 319 campaign, are presented in Figure 6 for the three values of the turbine-induced damping, i.e., for three
 320 turbines with different diameter. Incidentally, a methodology to dimension the turbine diameter from
 321 the values of the damping coefficient was developed by Pereiras *et al.* (2015). The efficiency matrices
 322 are expressed in terms of the C_{WR} ; this term is preferred over the absorbed power because, as a relative
 323 indicator, it removes the bias that would otherwise result from the fact that wave power is
 324 proportional to the square of the wave height.

325 The comparison between the three graphs shows a clear influence of the turbine-induced
 326 damping on the performance of the device: for individual energy bins there are variations in the C_{WR}
 327 of up to 40% depending on the value of the damping coefficient (e.g., $0 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 1 \text{ m}$,
 328 $5 \text{ s} < T_e < 6 \text{ s}$). However, given that the greater differences in the values of the C_{WR} are apparent only
 329 for the less powerful sea states (those with the lower values of wave height and small periods), it is
 330 expected that the overall influence of the turbine-induced damping on the energy captured by the
 331 OWC be lower.

332 The optimum value of the damping coefficient varies depending on the wave conditions. Thus,
 333 for sea states with small wave period ($T_e < 9 \text{ s}$) and low wave height ($H_{m0} < 3 \text{ m}$), the value of the
 334 damping coefficient that provides the higher values of C_{WR} is $B^* = 84.85$; in the case of sea states with
 335 larger periods ($T_e > 9 \text{ s}$) the value of the damping coefficient that provides the best efficiency is the

336 medium one ($B^* = 132.18$), or the largest one ($B^* = 160.49$) if the wave height is very low
 337 ($H_{m0} < 1$ m).

338

339 Figure 6. Efficiency matrices of the OWC wave energy converter expressed in terms of the capture
 340 width ratio (C_{WR}), given as a percentage, for the three values of the damping coefficient tested (for
 341 further clarification, the numeric value is also included).

342 The variation of C_{WR} amongst energy bins presents a similar distribution for the three values of
 343 the damping coefficient: a band of higher efficiency for sea states with energy period between 5 s and
 344 7 s, that decreases as wave height increases. Although the resonant period (that for which the C_{WR} is
 345 maximum) slightly increases when the damping coefficient increases, from $5 \text{ s} < T_e < 6 \text{ s}$ for
 346 $B^* = 84.85$ to $6 \text{ s} < T_e < 7 \text{ s}$ for $B^* = 132.18$ and 160.49 , the change is minimal and, for the studied
 347 range of damping values, does not enable an adjustment of the resonant period of the OWC by
 348 modifying the turbine-induced damping.

349 The efficiency matrices presented in Figure 6 characterise the OWC and, therefore, can be used
 350 to evaluate the pneumatic power production of the device in whatever location (with the limitation of
 351 having a similar water depth).

352 3.2. Energy captured by the OWC

353 The captured pneumatic energy matrices of the OWC are presented in Figure 7. These matrices are
 354 obtained by combining (energy bin by energy bin) the efficiency matrices of the OWC (Figure 6) with
 355 the wave resource characterisation matrices at the three study sites (Figure 2).

356

357 Figure 7. Captured energy matrices of the OWC per unit width of converter for the three values of the
 358 damping coefficient (B^*), at the three study sites. The colour scale represents the total pneumatic
 359 energy per metre of wave front (E_p) captured by the OWC in each energy bin; the numbers indicate the
 360 occurrence of the sea states in that energy bin, expressed in hours.

361 Comparing the results of annual captured energy (for whichever study site and value of the
 362 damping coefficient) with the efficiency matrix of the corresponding damping coefficient (Figure 6),
 363 it can be seen that energy bins with higher values of capture width ratio (those that comprise sea states

364 with energy period between 5 s and 7 s and low wave height) do not provide the bulk of captured
365 energy; in contrast, the variable that determines which energy bins provide the greatest amount of
366 captured energy is the available wave energy as provided by the site-specific characterisation matrices
367 (Figure 2). Thus, the energy bins providing the greatest amount of captured energy vary depending on
368 the study site: at site 1, they correspond to sea states with energy periods between 6 and 7 s; at site 2,
369 to sea states with periods between 8 and 9 s; and, finally, at site 3, to sea states with periods between
370 9 and 10 s. In the three cases, the energy bin that provides the largest captured energy comprises sea
371 states with a significant wave height between 1 and 2 m, which in turn correspond to those providing
372 the bulk of the wave energy resource (Section 2.1.1).

373 The influence of the turbine-induced damping is also noticeable. For example, at study site 1, the
374 bin providing the greatest amount of captured energy ($6 \text{ s} < T_e < 7 \text{ s}$, $1 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 2 \text{ m}$) with a total of
375 1.96 MWhm^{-1} for the lowest damping ($B^* = 84.85$) and 1.47 MWhm^{-1} for the largest one
376 ($B^* = 160.49$), which implies a reduction of more than 25% in the captured energy. Notwithstanding,
377 the energy bin that provides the greatest amount of captured energy is the same ($6 \text{ s} < T_e < 7 \text{ s}$,
378 $1 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 2 \text{ m}$) for the three values of the damping coefficient. At study site 2, the energy bin
379 providing the largest amount of captured energy (in this case $8 \text{ s} < T_e < 9 \text{ s}$, $1 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 2 \text{ m}$) is again
380 the same for the three values of the damping coefficient. However, at study site 3 the bin allowing the
381 greatest energy production differs depending on the turbine-induced damping considered: in the case
382 of $B^* = 132.18$ and 160.49 it corresponds to the interval delimited by $9 \text{ s} < T_e < 10 \text{ s}$ and
383 $1 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 2 \text{ m}$, and for $B^* = 84.85$ to the interval delimited by $7 \text{ s} < T_e < 8 \text{ s}$ and $0 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 1 \text{ m}$.

384 The results of the total annual available energy ($E_{w, \text{annual}}$) and the total annual captured energy
385 ($E_{p, \text{annual}}$), together with the annual capture width ratio ($C_{WR, \text{annual}}$), are presented in Figure 8. The
386 study site that provides the greatest amount of captured energy is Cariño (study site 1) with
387 8.7 MWhm^{-1} and an annual capture width ratio of 32.1%. At this location, the value of that damping
388 coefficient that performs best is the lowest ($B^* = 84.85$). Although site 1 presents a level of total
389 annual available energy equivalent to site 2 (27.14 vs 27.06 MWhm^{-1} , respectively), the total annual
390 captured energy in the former is greater. This is due to the fact that site 1 corresponds to the location
391 in which sea states of shorter energy periods ($T_e < 8 \text{ s}$) provide more energy (Figure 2), which in turn
392 are those with the largest efficiency (Figure 6). Therefore, an accurate wave resource characterisation
393 in the form of highly discretised wave-height-vs-energy-period matrix is of paramount importance for
394 assessing the energy production of an OWC wave energy converter.

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Figure 8. Comparison of the annual energy conversion performance of the OWC per unit width of converter for the three values of the damping coefficient (B^*), at the three study sites, expressed in terms of the total annual captured pneumatic energy (top graph, left axis) and of the annual capture width ratio (bottom graph). For reference, the total annual available wave energy is also represented in the top graph (right axis).

401

A wrong selection of the damping coefficient would reduce the total annual captured energy by 5% and 11% for the medium and largest values of the damping coefficient, respectively, which would have repercussions for the profitability of a wave farm. Furthermore, in this work in particular, there are two aspects that contribute to decrease the impact of the turbine-induced damping on the total annual captured energy: (i) the three values of the damping coefficient were chosen based on previous works (e.g., López *et al.*, 2016), so they present similar values, close to the overall optimum turbine-induced damping of the chamber; and (ii) as indicated above, the greater differences in the values of the C_{WR} correspond to sea states with short periods (Figure 6) which, for the study sites considered, do not provide the bulk of energy (Figure 2). This situation, though, may be different in other locations.

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Interestingly, the value of the damping coefficient that provides the greater performance in the study site 3 is the medium one ($B^* = 132.18$). The lowest damping, which provides the largest amount of energy production at study sites 1 and 2, descends to the second position in study site 3.

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Additionally, in the case of analysing the most appropriate location for a given turbine, it is found that for a turbine with damping coefficient $B^* = 84.85$ or $B^* = 132.18$ the best location corresponds to

414

415 study site 1, and for a turbine with a value of damping coefficient $B^* = 160.49$, study site 2 emerges
416 as the most appropriate one. This great variability points out the importance of correctly matching the
417 turbine-induced damping and the wave conditions that affect the OWC. It follows that an accurate
418 site-specific wave resource characterisation in the form of high-resolution characterisation matrices is
419 the first step towards a meaningful performance evaluation of an OWC wave energy converter.

420 Finally, the similarity between the annual captured width ratio at the three study sites (Figure 8 –
421 bottom) does not lead to similar values in the total annual captured energy (in particular, comparing
422 study site 3 with 1 and 2). This difference in the total annual captured energy is mainly connected to
423 the occurrence of the sea states in an energy bin, that varies substantially from one study site to
424 another (Figure 7) and emphasises, again, the importance of an accurate characterisation of the
425 available wave energy resource.

426 **4. Conclusions**

427 In this work, a comprehensive methodology to accurately evaluate the site-specific performance of an
428 OWC wave energy converter considering the turbine-induced damping together with usually
429 disregarded non-linear effects—in particular, the spring-like effect of air compressibility—is
430 presented. Thus, the novelty of this work lies not only in the results achieved but also in the
431 methodology presented, which constitutes an outcome on its own. The methodology is illustrated
432 through a case study in Galicia (NW Spain) in which three locations of interest are considered for
433 installing OWC technology.

434 The methodology is based on a combination of physical and numerical modelling. First, high-
435 resolution characterisation matrices considering virtually 100% of the exploitable resource are
436 computed at each site by implementing novel procedures based on the energy bin concept. Second,
437 small-scale physical model tests, in which air compressibility is appropriately considered, are carried
438 out to determine the efficiency matrices of the OWC for three different values of the turbine-induced
439 damping (i.e., three impulse turbines of different diameter); irregular wave conditions representative
440 of each energy bin were simulated, covering the virtual totality (> 99%) of the wave energy resource
441 in the characterisation matrices. Finally, resource and efficiency matrices were combined to obtain the
442 captured energy matrices that express, through a bivariate discretisation, the pneumatic energy that the
443 OWC captures for each turbine-induced damping at each site.

444 The methodology enables the selection of the most appropriate site and turbine-induced damping
445 combination based on performance values: of the three study sites considered, Cariño (1), Corme (2)
446 and Panxón (3), the best performance was attained at study site 1 with a total annual captured energy
447 of 8.7 MWhm^{-1} and an annual capture width ratio of 32.1%; the value of the damping coefficient that
448 performs best at this site was the lowest of those considered ($B^* = 84.85$). Moreover, the selection of
449 the best turbine for a given location is also possible: the value of the damping coefficient providing
450 the best performance at site 2 is also the lowest; unlike at site 3, where the medium value
451 ($B^* = 132.18$) yields the best results. Finally, the best site for a specific turbine can be also selected:
452 the best site for $B^* = 84.85$ and $B^* = 132.18$ was found to be site 1, and for $B^* = 160.49$, site 2. Going
453 beyond the methodology itself, the results showed that considering the turbine-induced damping is of
454 paramount importance in maximising the energy captured by an OWC device: when damping
455 coefficients changes, variations in the total annual energy captured of up to 11% were found, which
456 increase to 25% for individual energy bins. Furthermore, there is not a single optimum value of
457 turbine-induced damping for all sea states; indeed, the optimum depends on both the energy period
458 and the significant wave height. It follows that an accurate highly-discretised characterisation of the
459 wave energy resource is necessary. In addition, it was found that it is neither the capture width ratio
460 nor the power of the incoming sea states but the available wave energy provided by the site-specific
461 characterisation matrices that determines principally which energy bins provide the greatest amount of
462 annual captured energy, which highlights again the importance of the resource characterisation stage.

463 To sum up, the methodology presented in this work allows the accurate assessment of the
464 performance of an OWC wave energy converter at a specific coastal site, considering a highly-
465 discretised resource characterisation, non-linear effects, air compressibility effects and several levels
466 of turbine-induced damping. It constitutes the first step towards a wave-to-wire model in which non-
467 linear effects are thoroughly taken into account, with special emphasis on the influence of air
468 compressibility.

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